

One 4Health SURVEILLANCE

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Table of contents

Document history	2
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Methods	5
3. Evaluation Overview	7
4. Interim Evaluation Highlights	8
Action level indicators	8
Project level indicators	8
Need 1: Setting up and scaling up One Health surveillance	8
Need 2: Collaboration and sharing to avoid duplication of efforts and to ensure synergies	9
Surveillance activity level indicators	10
5. Towards One Health Surveillance: Facilitators and Barriers	11
5.1. Facilitators identified	11
5.2. Barriers and Challenges Identified	12
6. Recommendations	14
7. Conclusions	15

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Executive Summary

The OH4Surveillance project adopts a continuous, multi-level evaluation strategy designed to support iterative learning, responsiveness, and long-term sustainability. As detailed in Deliverable D3.1 (Evaluation Plan), the evaluation framework encompasses three interconnected levels. The evaluation activities of OH4Surveillance focus on action level, project level and surveillance activity level indicators. The methods of verification are adapted to each indicator.

This interim report outlines the progress of the evaluation activities conducted under Work Package 3 (WP3) of OH4Surveillance. WP3 is dedicated to continuous, formative evaluation throughout the project lifecycle, allowing timely reflection, feedback, and course correction across all work streams. Its aim is to ensure that the project remains aligned with its objectives and maximizes its potential impact.

Key evaluation activities to date have focused on a set of objective evaluation criteria, discussed with project partners during the Kick-off Meeting. These criteria, described in the Evaluation Plan (D3.1), serve as the backbone for the continuous monitoring across work packages. WP3 maintains close collaboration with other WPs to embed evaluation practices into routine project activities and foster an integrated learning approach.

Preliminary observations and findings suggest that the project is progressing steadily, with several early signs of success and impact. In particular, the usefulness of evaluation is clear.

Key identified facilitators include strong engagement from consortium partners, openness to reflective evaluation practices, and the early alignment of evaluation criteria with project deliverables. The planned use of the OH-EpiCap benchmarking tool¹ offers a structured avenue for both interim assessment and end-of-project re-evaluation.

In addition, several barriers have been identified. These include the varying familiarity with evaluation methods among participants, occasional delays in data flow between WPs, and the complexity of harmonizing evaluation inputs across diverse work streams and country contexts. These challenges are being addressed through iterative coordination and capacity-building efforts, and WP3 will continue to refine the evaluation framework as the project evolves.

¹ [OH-EpiCap Tool](https://freddietafreeth.shinyapps.io/OH-EpiCap/) <https://freddietafreeth.shinyapps.io/OH-EpiCap/>

1. Introduction

The majority of new emerging infectious diseases that affect humans are zoonoses, infections that can be transmitted between animals and humans. There are many factors that drive the emergence and spread of zoonotic diseases, and it has become evident that animal health, human health and the environment are interconnected. Therefore, there is a pressing need for more rapid and effective responses to zoonotic diseases, which can be achieved with a conceptual shift from siloed approaches towards a One Health approach. The surveillance on the animal health side and in the environment need to be scaled up to set up a One Health surveillance for emerging and re-emerging pathogens. Ideally, this is done in collaboration across countries.

The general objective of OH4Surveillance ('Setting up a coordinated surveillance under the One Health approach') is to support the participating countries to set up and scale up One Health surveillance to priority pathogens in an efficient, coordinated and collaborative manner. The project includes capacity building and surveillance activities. OH4Surveillance comprises of 11 beneficiaries and 11 affiliated entities and is coordinated by Statens Serum Institut (SSI).

The OH4Surveillance project aims to support participating countries in setting up and scaling up coordinated surveillance under the One Health approach, with a specific focus on prioritized emerging and re-emerging zoonotic pathogens. In this context, evaluation plays a central role, not only in assessing progress but also in fostering learning, responsiveness, and alignment across countries, sectors, and work streams.

This interim evaluation report covers the first 18 months of the 3-year project and is produced under Work Package 3 (WP3), which leads the evaluation activities of the project. The aim of this report is to summarize the evaluation activities conducted during the first half of the project, highlight key findings and observations, and support strategic reflection across the consortium. The evaluation takes place continuously throughout the project, ensuring that relevant insights are captured and acted upon in real time.

2. Methods

Work package 3 of OH4Surveillance is responsible for the evaluation of the project and works closely with other work packages. The key strategy applied is that evaluation takes place throughout the project, thus allowing addressing relevant observations during the project lifetime. In line with this, evaluation was among the key topics discussed at Kick-off meeting of OH4Surveillance, held in Copenhagen, Denmark, on February 27-28, 2024 and the project meeting in Uppsala Sweden 25-26 February 2025. The evaluation activities of OH4Surveillance will focus on action level, project level and surveillance activity level indicators. The methods of verification are adapted to each indicator. The Key Performance Indicators reflect the action level indicators and have numerical target values. The results of the evaluation activities are reported in the Interim Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.2) and in the Final Evaluation Report (Deliverable D3.3).

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The methodology used to gather evaluation insights reflects the multi-level evaluation framework established in Deliverable D3.1. Insights have been gathered through internal consultations, monitoring of WP activities and consortium discussions, and a questionnaire that was shared during the project meeting in Uppsala in February 2025.

The questionnaire was targeting project participants. Questions were open-ended and responses were anonymous. The survey gathered responses from 35 participants representing all partner countries, a wide geographical range and a diversity of institutional perspectives. The questionnaire also supported monitoring of WP4 Sustainability activities and contributed towards Deliverable 4.1 'Interim Sustainability report'.

WP3 works closely with other work packages to integrate evaluation into routine project work and to support feedback loops for ongoing adjustments. This report lays the foundation for continued learning and performance tracking in preparation for the final evaluation report (D3.3).

3. Evaluation Overview

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) reflect the action level indicators and have numerical target values. Project level indicators are the Specific Objectives that OH4Surveillance aims to reach to address the key needs identified, and the related Key Performance Indicators. The third evaluation level is the surveillance activity level, focusing on specific surveillance activities targeting a specific pathogen or disease.

For the surveillance activity level, an established tool for evaluating One Healthness of surveillance systems is used. The tool, OH-EpiCap tool (Tegegne et al., 2023), was developed during the One Health European Joint Programme (European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, Grant Agreement No. 773830) Joint Integrative Project MATRIX. The tool can be applied to any system where some multi-sectoral collaboration exists at any step of the surveillance, regardless of the level of formalization of the surveillance activity. The evaluation consists of three dimensions, each targeting four indicators.

This structured multi-level approach ensures that evaluation is not a one-time activity but an ongoing process that informs project implementation and fosters sustainability beyond the project's lifespan.

4. Interim Evaluation Highlights

The project is progressing according to the planned timeline and remains on track. All key activities are being implemented as scheduled, and the project continues to meet established quantitative KPIs and formalized performance criteria. At this stage, there are no foreseen deviations to report.

Action level indicators

Several of the key quantitative aspects such as the number of zoonotic pathogens covered, countries involved, capacity-building initiatives conducted, and samples tested have been already reached.

Project level indicators

Need 1: Setting up and scaling up One Health surveillance

Specific objective 1: “Obtain an overview of current One Health surveillance and surveillance needs for selected priority pathogens in the participating countries”

Several respondents affirmed increased understanding, particularly through exposure to challenges in other countries and cross-country comparisons, related to the working group activities. Given the cross-border nature of the targeted zoonotic health threats, addressing Need 1 is effective through international collaboration.

Examples of responses:

“Yes. Useful to get overview between countries plus what areas need improvement.”

“Yes, seeing the activities of other countries was helpful.”

Specific objective 2: “Set up and scale up One Health surveillance activities addressing regional and country-specific needs”

Several responses noted existing or improved structures (e.g., *“Zoonosis expert network,” “More building on existing collaborations”*). Others indicated partial establishment or ongoing efforts, reflecting different country-specific starting points.

Concerns about funding and critical mass were noted (*“No funding for sustained activities,” “Need focus on critical surveillance issues”*), and challenges to sustainability were mentioned already at this point. These insights reflect real-world barriers to scaling up.

Specific Objective 3: “Contribute to harmonising and collaborative approaches across countries to prepare for cross-border health threats”

Recurring themes mentioned in the responses included joint policy development, regular meetings, and increased communication. Examples:

“Joint policy strategies,” “More exchanges with public health authorities,” “Funding for these activities.”

Responses further included considerations on funding, enhanced communication, and stronger collaboration between human health and animal health sectors. These responses reflect the underlying systems and needs.

The responses offered grounded suggestions for improving interoperability and collaboration, demonstrating that the questionnaire captured input relevant to harmonisation goals.

Need 2: Collaboration and sharing to avoid duplication of efforts and to ensure synergies

Specific objective 4: “Establish structures and processes for collaboration and sharing of experiences among countries participating in OH4Surveillance”

Multiple respondents acknowledged the value of exposure to other countries’ experiences:

“Yes, seeing the activities of other countries was helpful.”

“Useful to get overview between countries plus what areas need improvement.”

This indicates learning and information flow across the participating countries. The reported frequent involvement in working group meetings and capacity building initiatives suggested structured engagement. These interactions are channels through which shared learning occurs.

Both formal and informal processes for sharing experiences across countries are in place under this project and are perceived as valuable, addressing this objective.

Specific Objective 5: “Establish structures and processes for collaboration with stakeholders at national, EU and international levels”

Responses to questions related to which extent structures and processes for collaboration with stakeholders are in place at national level included:

“Yes, Zoonosis expert network,”

“More building up on existing formal collaborations,”

“Partly, we have some structures already in place.”

The comments indicated both existing and evolving collaborations, in particular with national-level stakeholders. There was clear evidence of both existing structures and aspirations to deepen collaboration with external stakeholders, supporting this objective.

Specific Objective 6: “Establish structures and processes for disseminating experiences to support countries that are not part of OH4Surveillance”

This objective is supported by activities coordinated by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), where the countries involved in OH4Surveillance actively attend. Moreover, the coordinator of OH4Surveillance has been invited to attend consortium meetings of sister consortia.

The questionnaire revealed several transferable lessons; uncertainty about long-term sustainability and funding can be limiting factors for broader dissemination.

Surveillance activity level indicators

In the initial planning of OH4Surveillance, the primary surveillance activity indicator was the use of the OH-EpiCap tool. Its application across participating countries was designed to provide a harmonized framework for evaluating surveillance systems, enabling benchmarking across pathogens and countries. This supported a common direction and allowed for structured reflection, particularly as countries were concurrently setting up and scaling up their surveillance efforts for animal and environmental health, with the overarching aim of informing the public health sector. Work package 3 Evaluation hosted two webinars during year 1 (2024) to facilitate the capacity building in each country to conduct these evaluations throughout the lifespan of the project. Based on feedback at the General Assembly in February 2025, it was evident that there still persists a need to onboard a few countries to this activity, hence at least one additional webinar is planned for year 2 (2025).

During implementation of the project, an additional activity emerged in response to early project insights: the formation of pathogen-specific working groups across countries that was implemented by WP5 in direct connection to the surveillance activities. These groups were developed to facilitate experience sharing and discussion around practical implementation challenges and solutions. Over time, they have supported the organization of cross-country capacity-building workshops and have become a highly valuable complementary component to the evaluation activities.

Together, the use of the OH-EpiCap tool and the pathogen-specific working groups have proven mutually reinforcing. While the tool offers a structured approach to evaluation, the working groups have enabled more applied, topic-specific collaboration and exchange. This combination has supported progress towards Need 1 and Specific Objectives 1–3, by contributing to improved coordination, mutual learning, and enhanced regional surveillance capacity building, linked directly to Key performance Indicator 3 and 8.

Work Package 3 continues to support efforts through training webinars in terms of evaluations through the OH-EpiCap tool, and the working groups remain anchored under WP5 in close relation to the surveillance activities.

The details of these activities and the output in relation to each surveillance activities are included in the Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2.

5. Towards One Health Surveillance: Facilitators and Barriers

The evaluation activities conducted during the first 18 months of OH4Surveillance have already revealed a number of internal and external factors that can facilitate or hinder progress toward building more adaptive integrated surveillance systems under the One Health framework. The facilitators have supported countries in strengthening their institutional capacities and fostering a culture of continuous assessment and improvement, while the barriers are something that should be addressed to ensure sustainability.

5.1. Facilitators identified

Common Needs

Each country selected the pathogens they focus on, but there is major positive overlap in the target pathogens. This means both opportunities for working together and potential for impact that is more than what improvements in a single country could achieve.

Structures for Sharing and Learning

The working groups have been very useful for sharing experiences. Participation is active.

Building on existing structures

Several participating countries are building upon existing national structures for surveillance, coordination, or intersectoral collaboration. These pre-established frameworks — whether formal or informal — provide a valuable foundation for the One Health approach, reducing the need to start from scratch and allowing countries to adapt and expand systems that are already embedded in their institutional landscapes.

Evaluation

The evaluation process itself has emerged as a facilitator: several countries have reported growing confidence and capacity in conducting self-assessments of their surveillance systems' capacity. This reflects a crucial shift — from compliance-driven reporting to a more reflexive mode of governance, in which Member States critically examine their systems' relevance, agility, and long-term sustainability. This self-reflective capacity is essential for operating within dynamic socio-ecological systems, where both threats and institutional contexts evolve over time.

Collaboration and Synergies

Collaboration and knowledge exchange with EFSA and other projects from the same call have enhanced the relevance and visibility of OH4Surveillance outputs. These connections have encouraged harmonization of indicators and reporting standards, and they have reinforced the credibility of national efforts by linking them to Europe-wide risk assessment

processes. Synergies with parallel initiatives have helped avoid duplication and enabled cross-project learning.

5.2. Barriers and Challenges Identified

The interim evaluation has surfaced several barriers that affect the progress and sustainability of One Health surveillance efforts across the OH4Surveillance partner countries. These challenges span organizational, technical, policy, and cross-border dimensions, and reflect both structural limitations and dynamic conditions at the national and international levels.

Organizational Barriers

A prominent theme emerging from the responses was the lack of stable, long-term funding mechanisms, which hinders the institutionalization of surveillance practices introduced or strengthened during the project. This funding uncertainty affects not only the continuation of activities but also undermines the motivation and retention of key personnel. Staff turnover remains a concern in some countries, posing risks to institutional memory and continuity, especially where formal documentation and knowledge-sharing practices are weak.

While several countries are building on existing collaboration structures, others reported that stakeholder engagement remains fragmented or reliant on informal professional networks. This variability in organizational maturity affects the ability to coordinate effectively across sectors and to embed One Health approaches into routine operations.

The project is explicitly designed to support surveillance activities that are not already covered by national mandates. While this ensures complementarity, it also creates a dependency on political commitment and administrative flexibility at the national level. Establishing new mandates or expanding priorities requires considerable political and institutional effort, which may not be feasible in the absence of long-term external funding. There is currently a gap in both defining and funding such mandates in several countries.

Without sustained funding and institutional support, there is a risk that the collaborative structures and evaluation mechanisms established during the project may not be maintained. This highlights the need for a strategic communication focus in the remaining project period, aimed at increasing political awareness and fostering ownership at the national level.

Technical Barriers

Technical limitations continue to constrain the integration and effectiveness of surveillance activities. Data interoperability including differences in terminology, reporting formats, and access rights emerged as a central challenge, particularly in countries where data systems remain siloed across sectors. Even where intersectoral interest is high, infrastructure gaps (e.g., limited IT capacity, lack of standardized digital tools) reduce the ability to analyse, share, and act on data in a timely and integrated manner.

The process of surveillance data reporting remains a significant bottleneck. The complexity of data systems, along with the time-intensive nature of collating, validating, and interpreting data across sectors, means that reporting is unlikely to be prioritized unless adequate funding and staffing are in place. This issue is further compounded by limited interoperability between existing surveillance frameworks.

A specific example raised by several partners is the challenge of uploading surveillance data to EFSA using the SIGMA tool and MicroStrategy platform. While these systems are intended to harmonize EU-wide data flows, they have proven to be technically complex, time-consuming, and resource-intensive. Many partners report steep learning curves and operational bottlenecks in working with these platforms, which pose a significant barrier to regular or real-time data submission.

The current approach to data submission is not well aligned with long-term sustainability goals. Without dedicated funding and technical support beyond the project period, it is unlikely that all countries will be able to maintain consistent data uploads. This creates a risk of fragmentation and undermines the objective of developing a cohesive and responsive surveillance infrastructure across countries.

In some countries, the burden of multiple reporting demands and limited human resources could lead to disengagement from evaluation and reporting activities. Streamlined processes and integration with existing systems may help mitigate this risk.

Policy and Regulatory Challenges

The evaluation also pointed to a number of policy and legal bottlenecks. These include a lack of formal mandates for One Health collaboration in national legislation, which limits the enforceability and strategic prioritization of intersectoral coordination. In some contexts, overlapping or unclear roles between ministries and agencies create friction, leading to duplication or gaps in surveillance activities.

There is also limited harmonization of data governance frameworks, especially when it comes to ethical, legal, and procedural standards for sharing sensitive or sector-specific data. This can slow down collaboration, even when there is willingness to engage.

Cross-Border Challenges

Finally, the project has identified several cross-border barriers that may impede the broader goal of building a cohesive European surveillance system. One challenge is the asymmetry in capacities and readiness levels among participating countries. While some partners have long-standing infrastructure and intersectoral protocols in place, others are still building foundational systems. This divergence can make it difficult to apply shared tools or to benefit fully from peer learning opportunities.

In addition, language, administrative diversity, and variable levels of political commitment to One Health priorities contribute to coordination challenges at the international level. These differences underscore the need for flexible, context-sensitive strategies when fostering cross-country alignment and collaboration.

6. Recommendations

Strengthen Mandates and Ownership

A key challenge remains the lack of formal mandates and prioritization for surveillance activities not already covered by national obligations. Establishing clear national mandates backed by policy alignment and inter-ministerial coordination is essential. Where possible, national strategies should include surveillance as a defined priority area across sectors, supported by legislative or regulatory frameworks.

Secure Long-Term and Flexible Funding Mechanisms

The complexity and time investment required for comprehensive surveillance and reporting are unlikely to be sustained without dedicated funding. Multi-year, flexible funding at both EU and national levels is needed to support integrated surveillance development, stakeholder engagement, and data interoperability. Funding instruments should also consider the operational realities of smaller or less-resourced countries.

Invest in Strategic and Political Engagement

Targeted communication efforts are needed to raise awareness of the relevance and impact of One Health surveillance. The project should prioritize engagement with policymakers, senior administrators, and national budget holders during its remaining phase, to lay the groundwork for institutionalization and continued investment beyond the current funding cycle.

Formalize and Consolidate Collaboration Structures

While many countries demonstrate ongoing cross-sectoral coordination, efforts often remain informal or fragmented. Establishing or strengthening formal coordination mechanisms such as national One Health platforms, inter-agency task forces, or memoranda of understanding can improve continuity, role clarity, and accountability.

Enhance Cross-Country and Technical Exchange

The success of pathogen-specific working groups highlights the value of structured, topic-specific collaboration. These groups should be further developed and institutionalized as forums for experience sharing, capacity building, and joint planning. Workshops and continued facilitation support can ensure sustainability and alignment.

Address Technical and Human Resource Capacity Gaps

Improving the reporting and encouraging efforts towards interoperability are important. Targeted capacity building, including human resources, remains essential. Support should be tailored to national contexts, with an emphasis on practical skills and applied knowledge transfer.

7. Conclusions

The OH4Surveillance project demonstrates that structured evaluation, combined with flexible, needs-driven collaboration, can produce tangible progress in building One Health surveillance capacity. A key strength of the project has been its decision to integrate evaluation as a continuous process, rather than a retrospective exercise. This has allowed early identification of gaps and opportunities and has provided the basis for timely strategic adjustments.

One of the most significant insights at this stage in the project is the recognition that while technical capacity is advancing, political prioritisation and mandate establishment remain critical gaps. Surveillance activities outside existing national obligations require clear political will, cross-sectoral alignment, and secure funding mechanisms. The absence of national funding for such activities poses a systemic, structural challenge, which can only be addressed through sustained dialogue and policy-level engagement.

As the project moves into its final phases, a strong emphasis on communication, political engagement, and awareness-raising will be essential. These efforts should aim to solidify national ownership, inform policy development, and ensure that the systems and structures created under OH4Surveillance can be sustained and expanded beyond the project's lifecycle.

The ability to reach these insights within the current project timeframe underscores the effectiveness of the project's innovative evaluation approach and provides a strong foundation for strengthening resilience and ensuring long-term sustainability.

